

Integrating Waste Control at Major Events Through Application of Fun Theory

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INTRODUCTION

The project was based off the 'Roskilde Entrepreneurs' initiative that wanted to better the waste handling at Roskilde Festival. The purpose was a change of attitude towards how the guests perceive the waste they produce at the festival in order to minimise the local environmental impact of the event. To meet this purpose a mechatronic interactive environment was designed and built at one of the Agoras at Roskilde where trash could be traded for events.

THE PROJECT

The project added to the realm of 'Fun Theory' with the dogma that people will do a task if it is fun to do. By incorporating art and design into a trash can, the task of collecting and handing in waste from the festival was rewarded with funny events. The trash can 'Trashy the Robot' was constructed off second hand building materials, as well as about 90% recycled electronics. By Designing and prototyping a mechatronic system of microcontrollers, infrared sensors, an old computer, and two old LCD screens, the robot would thank people when they put trash in his mouth. He would look at people with two animated eyes at the LCD displays as well as trigger random events with light, smoke, and sound. See Figure 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Robot was a success in getting attention to the need for waste handling. Guests went to their camps and cleaned up only to put the waste in Trashy's mouth. The area around Trashy was crowded all evening due to the light and event when people put waste in it. The concept of integrating waste handling into the entertainment is a whole new way of understanding 'green' and a way of handling the overall impact of major event. This can be rolled out to other major events that produce trash, like Distortion, sports events, and concerts.

Figure 1: Trashy the Robot in action late Thursday at Roskilde Festival